

THE NEED AND FEATURES OF USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE ACTIVITIES OF THE PROSECUTOR'S OFFICE

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ANNOTATION

This article examines the need and specifics of using artificial intelligence in the activities of the prosecutor's office, the level of electronic transformation through analysis and digitalization of the activities of the prosecutor's office in Uzbekistan. In foreign countries, attention is paid to the strengths of the practice of implementing and applying artificial intelligence in the prosecutor's office. The importance of analyzing the experience of interaction with digital systems and their implementation in the activities of the Prosecutor's Office of Uzbekistan, improving the activities of prosecutor's offices in this direction, is noted. Also, some scientific conclusions have been developed and proposals have been put forward on the digitalization of the activities of the prosecutor's office and the application of artificial intelligence in foreign countries.

Key words: artificial intelligence, electronic circulation, digitalization, information cooperation, international experience, comparative legal analysis.

It's no secret that in our country, as in various fields, special attention is being paid to the potential use of artificial intelligence in the work of prosecutorial authorities. In particular, Decree No. 6079 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 5, 2020, "On Approval of the Digital Uzbekistan – 2030 Strategy and Measures for its Effective Implementation" provides for the implementation of comprehensive measures to actively develop the digital economy in our country and the widespread adoption of modern information and communication technologies across all sectors and areas [1]. The Action Plan for 2025 of the "Uzbekistan 2030" Strategy for creating decent conditions for realizing the potential of each person notes the need to develop a draft regulatory legal act on the implementation of information technology at the pre-trial stage of proceedings and to specify mechanisms for the use of artificial intelligence technologies in the classification of crimes [2].

Despite the existence of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 2433 of November 16, 2015, "On measures for the further implementation of modern information and communication technologies in the activities of prosecutorial authorities" and Resolution No. PP-2568 of July 29, 2016, "On measures for the widespread implementation of information and communication technologies in the activities of the prosecutor's office of the Republic of Uzbekistan," the objectives set in these decrees do not allow for the full and effective implementation of artificial intelligence in the activities of prosecutorial authorities. The effectiveness of prosecutorial oversight functions is closely linked to the work of the structures under its control. Despite numerous planned development areas, achieving certain goals is hampered by various objective factors. The traditional circulation of paper documents between prosecutor's offices and departmental organizations at various levels is an obstacle that significantly slows the process of digital transformation in this sector. In the era

of technology and science, artificial intelligence has become the center of heated debate and attracts the attention of many. This cutting-edge tool opens up new opportunities for optimizing the work of government agencies, particularly the prosecutor's office. Protecting citizens' legitimate interests and maintaining law and order require the constant development of methodological frameworks and the implementation of innovative approaches. The prosecutor's office, as a key element of the state system, performs the important task of upholding the rule of law and protecting citizens' rights and freedoms. The use of artificial intelligence can significantly enhance the potential of prosecutorial oversight and elevate its effectiveness to a whole new level. From a philosophical perspective, artificial intelligence is not limited to rational thinking. Graphical thinking can also contribute to the development of artificial intelligence. Mathematics is embedded in both language and thought, and the subject of artificial intelligence must also possess mathematical tools [3]. The types of technologies currently used in the legal field are virtually identical. Most are based on deep learning, natural language processing, text and image recognition, and other technologies. Depending on the volume of "learned" data, the depth and accuracy of the generated content also varies. The content type typically consists of numerical or logically related information [4].

Chinese scientists write that there are many artificial intelligence algorithms used in investigations and forensics, including neural networks, particle swarm algorithms, genetic algorithms, mathematical optimization methods, simulation-based mitigation, optimal flow algorithms, expert systems, etc. [5]. Thus, while there are numerous opportunities for using artificial intelligence algorithms in the legal sphere, their practical application is limited.

In today's reality, digitalization may also require a complete legal overhaul of the prosecutor's office. In particular, the development of rules for remote interaction

with citizens, including online registration for receiving and submitting electronic requests, is becoming increasingly important. Rejecting duplicate requests or creating standardized responses to requests with identical content will save time and reduce costs, optimize the work of prosecutors, and simplify the processing of electronic requests. For example, to simplify the search for electronic requests and information on their processing time, it is possible to implement a search and tracking function for internal requests from citizens and organizations, accessible to all citizens on online portals. Within this area of digitalization, special attention should be paid to the issue of mandatory verification of the applicant's email address. Any postal address can be used to submit an application or send a letter to any address, including the district prosecutor's office. This leads to a large volume of anonymous letters. Given the rise of digital crime and abuse of the right to petition, many remote requests are anonymous. This opens up the possibility of implementing artificial intelligence to prevent anonymous electronic requests by requiring a personal identification test to distinguish them from bots, or by confirming the letter with a reply to the specified email address. However, it is worth noting that this work must be comprehensive and encompass prosecutor's offices at all levels. The introduction of artificial intelligence into prosecutor's offices for remotely receiving and reviewing citizen requests would radically simplify their work without requiring significant financial investment. It is undoubtedly true that today there is a need to integrate digital technologies into prosecutor's offices, not only for receiving applications but also for scheduling remote appointments with the prosecutor's office, as well as to regulate software requirements. This involves identifying applicants and establishing a clear procedure for submitting applications electronically to prevent duplicate applications and reduce the burden on prosecutorial authorities in this area.

One of the pressing issues today is studying the experience of developed countries in using artificial intelligence in the work of the prosecutor's office of the Republic of Uzbekistan and incorporating its positive aspects into the legislation and law enforcement practices of our country. Law enforcement agencies around the world are actively incorporating advanced technologies into their work. Artificial intelligence is demonstrating impressive results and is becoming an indispensable assistant in the legal sphere.

China's economy is one of the fastest-growing countries. The People's Republic of China is also embracing digital technologies in the prosecution service. This is evidenced by the introduction of an artificial intelligence-based prosecutorial system in China—a robot prosecutor. This system has an algorithm that allows it to analyze situations and draw conclusions about a person's guilt or innocence. Currently, the robot prosecutor makes decisions based on the analysis of thousands of cases and previous decisions on similar cases included in its program. In terms of effectiveness, in 2021, the artificial intelligence system, known as the "robot prosecutor" in the Shanghai People's Prosecutor's Office, accurately drafted 97% of criminal indictments heard by Shanghai courts from 2015 to 2020. In China, we can also observe the writing of complex procedural documents by artificial intelligence, which analyzes legal practice and drafts reports using appropriate algorithms [6].

However, the information security of the "robot prosecutor" and its uninterrupted operation are not yet fully guaranteed in practice, and the use of artificial intelligence in the Chinese prosecutor's office, according to open sources, is still in experimental mode.

The United Arab Emirates, where "smart systems" successfully implement fines and analyze criminal situations to prevent crimes, is also a case in point.

In the CIS countries, digitalization is rapidly developing and artificial intelligence systems are being implemented. Kazakhstan is presenting its path to

digital transformation as part of the special state initiative "Digital Kazakhstan." Recently, scientific and technological changes have been taking place in Kazakhstan's judicial system.

The digital revolution in the judicial system began with the introduction of artificial intelligence (AI) as assistants for justice officials. Investigators are already receiving assistance from intelligent systems within the "Electronic Case" platform developed by the Prosecutor's Office. AI helps identify substances used and plan investigative actions. The innovative "Digital Analysis of Judicial Practice" tool deserves special attention. This system is capable of not only analyzing existing judicial systems but also predicting the likely outcomes of civil litigation. Judges can now obtain new information about similar precedents when considering new cases, significantly streamlining judicial proceedings.

South Korea has achieved significant results, where artificial intelligence not only monitors hidden transactions and illegal securities operations and monitors the financial sector, but also helps prevent potential suicides and save lives.

AI should be increasingly integrated into the work of prosecutors to automate routine tasks, analyze large volumes of data, and identify patterns in criminal investigations. AI helps organize documents, search and track information, and can also be used for crime prediction and behavioral analysis.

Prosecutors' work is diverse, and there are ample opportunities for the effective use of artificial intelligence (AI). For example, AI can be used in pre-investigation review and analysis of criminal cases: quickly searching and analyzing databases, identifying similarities and connections in crimes, and automatically analyzing video, audio, and images. AI can also be used in the analysis of forensic practices: it can ensure consistency in law enforcement practices by analyzing court decisions and prosecutorial opinions, as well as automatically selecting precedents and legal norms. Corruption and economic crime prevention: identifies suspicious

patterns in public procurement and financial transactions, predicts illegal activity in tax and financial information. Crime prevention: predicts the likelihood of crimes using geoanalytics, assesses crime rates by region, and develops preventative measures. Handling citizen inquiries: automatically differentiates and classifies inquiries, identifies duplicates and fabricated claims, and provides automated assistance in preparing responses to inquiries. Improving internal operational efficiency: manages electronic document management and archives, analyzes and optimizes employee workload, and identifies cyberthreats in the area of information security.

The potential uses of artificial intelligence in the prosecutor's office include the following:

Artificial intelligence enables the automation of daily bureaucratic processes and the systematization of large volumes of documents and information, significantly speeding up work;

Artificial intelligence can quickly analyze data and identify hidden patterns, facilitating criminal investigations and crime prevention;

Artificial intelligence-based systems can monitor information from the internet and other sources, facilitating evidence collection.

Artificial intelligence enables the early detection of potential crimes by identifying behavioral patterns.

It can be concluded that the digitalization of prosecutorial activities is one of the most important tasks related to law enforcement, ensuring that cases are conducted in accordance with the principles of transparency and fairness.

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